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METHODOLOGY FOR THE FORMATION OF THE CONCEPT OF "GREEN ENERGY" IN PHYSICS AT SECONDARY SCHOOL

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Abstract: *In the article the importance of studying alternative energy sources in secondary schools is discussed, their potential in education, as well as what method is recommended to use. An effective way to form ideas about green energy in primary school students is to develop a program in this area and organize projects to implement it. The educational material on "green energy" also reveals the role of physics and technology in the development of the energy field. The creation of the "Technopark" project can be an impetus for the training of future specialists in the field of energy. The article lists the main principles of the project of the technology park.*

Keywords: *concepts, green energy, project, technology park, secondary school, physics, renewable energy.*

Introduction

One of the main reasons for the insufficient dissemination of renewable energy technologies is the lack of human resources with the necessary knowledge and skills in this area of energy [2]. To eliminate these shortcomings, a sufficient number of well-trained specialists is needed. Naturally, specialists are needed for resource assessment, system development and design, installation, operation, repair and maintenance, information processing, etc. With the development of information technology, the need for an increase in the workforce increases, which is one of the critical factors in the implementation of any strategy. Therefore, education is one of the main means for solving problems. Renewable energy education addresses various topics and issues related to renewable energy sources and technologies. The main goals of renewable energy education are to provide functional knowledge and understanding of facts, concepts, principles and technologies for the use of renewable energy sources. Therefore, depending on the level, the role of the educational program in the field of renewable energy sources should be educational, informative, research and creative. The objectives of the educational program in this area include developing students' awareness of the nature and causes of energy problems facing humanity, familiarizing students with various types of non-renewable and renewable energy sources, motivating and preparing students to make efforts to develop and implement alternative strategies to address the problems facing the energy sector [2].

The future well-being of humanity depends on its ability to wisely utilize currently existing non-renewable energy resources and utilize new and renewable energy sources. One of the most important responsibilities of the current generation of secondary school teachers is to present the concept of energy and green energy at the school level in a correct and accessible manner for students of a certain age in order to promote understanding of all the complex issues related to energy and motivate them to find the right solutions.

Efforts should be made to improve students' knowledge and understanding of renewable energy sources and technologies, familiarize them with the relevance, with the problems of using renewable energy sources at the school level. It is at the school level that interest and preference for renewable energy technologies can be demonstrated. Some attempts in this direction have already been made and described in the literature [3-5]. The authors of [3-5] proposed a program for potential levels of education in the field of renewable energy sources. For students aged 13–16, relevant concepts and demonstration experiments were introduced into the programs of natural sciences and biology, preparatory courses in the field of renewable energy technologies were introduced, for students aged

15–18, laboratory experiments were also introduced into the programs of physics, chemistry and biology, and professional courses in the field of renewable energy technologies were introduced. As early as 1978, a lecture laboratory program for teaching alternative and renewable energy sources in the high school industrial arts laboratory was developed at Montclair State College in New Jersey, USA [6]. The goal of the course was to provide students with an idea of the identification of specific energy sources and their potential. Similarly, the Moscow Institute of New Technologies has introduced a course for secondary and educational solar laboratories [7], and in 1990 secondary school students in Victoria, Australia were invited to design, build and present models of solar cars in competition with each other [8]. A significant amount of work in energy education at the school level has also been carried out at the Florida Solar Energy Center, USA [9].

The Lebanese Ministry of Education has reviewed and reduced some parts of the courses in the curriculum of the supplementary and primary grades, while replacing them with others that are necessary and useful. These courses will aim to introduce students to the concept of renewable energy, its applications and its advantages at a very early stage. (ICM_paper.pdf). A good example to illustrate this point is the experiment carried out by students in grade 9. In grade 9, electricity takes on a whole new meaning, given that the student reaches a good level of scientific maturity. And this makes him capable of better understanding the concept of renewable energy, devising ways to conduct a complete experiment where the main result will be a certain conclusion of the actual number.

Students, after completing this training, will have their own ideas, studies or community in the near future, will be able to present a short scientific report. All this allows students to act in society as an individual.

As we know, the pandemic has served as a catalyst for identifying the existing gaps in the education infrastructure for sustainable development. One of these gaps is the lack of education and courses in the field of renewable energy at the secondary level. The lack of education in this field at the secondary school level (age 11-18) explains the negative dissemination of renewable energy technologies, especially among ordinary people [10]. Factors such as socio-cultural, technological barriers persist among the public due to the weak dissemination of education in the field of renewable technologies. To overcome the barriers, it is necessary to study new methods of using energy from new sources by using cost-effective technologies. One of the strategies to achieve this goal is to introduce renewable energy concepts in secondary schools. In this way, many future citizens will be informed about the serious need for renewable energy technologies, and motivated to develop new creative and technological innovations in this field [11].

Secondary education in renewable energy plays a significant role. Because the subjects taught in secondary schools affect the interest of students. Teaching middle-level subjects in a structured manner can increase students' interest in studying related fields. Students choose specific courses in their higher education institutions based on their level of interest in that subject [12,13]. Having science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) subjects in high schools increases students' interest in careers [14].

In addition to industrial and higher education, in the secondary schools also teach various energy production methods, including solar, wind, hydro, geothermal and biofuel. Because ideas about energy production and green energy should be formed from school age. In this way, environmental protection is formed in the future generation. Therefore, knowledge of energy production methods and the formation of interest in this area in the future is the primary responsibility of secondary school teachers. In addition to the above methods, there are also alternative energy sources, such as hydrogen energy and cryogenics.

As you know, there are several sources of energy: renewable, non-renewable and alternative energy sources. Renewable energy sources include:

1. Solar energy: using solar panels to convert sunlight into electrical energy.
2. Wind energy: using wind turbines to convert wind energy into electricity.
3. Hydropower: using the energy of moving water (rivers) to generate electricity.
4. Geothermal energy: using the heat of the earth to generate heat or electricity.

5. Biofuels: using organic materials (such as plant residues) to produce fuel.

It should be noted that this was the first time that human muscle power was used (for instance, lifting a load) [15].

Later, people decided to extract energy using natural phenomena. This is also thunderstorm energy, that is, they used lightning energy to generate electricity.

Space energy: solar energy in space was used to generate electricity for artificial satellites.

The education of students in the elementary culture of careful energy use begins in early childhood and continues throughout the school period. The main task of teachers at school is to help students acquire basic knowledge appropriate to their age. Therefore, it is necessary to provide information about energy, its role and importance in human life, the rules for the efficient and economical use of energy resources, the impact of energy production and consumption on the environment [1]. It is necessary to draw up plans and build projects and create the necessary conditions for students to understand efficient energy use and to cultivate in them responsibility for an economical and careful attitude to electricity, heat, water, and nature in general.

It is necessary to familiarize students with basic methods and means of energy conservation and saving; to promote the formation of students' belief in the importance of personal contribution to energy conservation; to develop the skills and abilities of scientific research, and the skills of creative thinking.

Taking into account the age, select the forms and methods of training and education. The game form of training is effective, because in such classes, students are active participants in the educational process, are in the process of constant activity. It is recommended to train through active forms of work, practical activities, setting up experiments, conducting elementary types of research work, independent activity of the student, which allows him to become a subject of the educational process. In these conditions, the pedagogical worker is a coordinator, consultant, assistant, directing the process of training and education.

Projects at the secondary level

Of course, every event has both positive and negative sides. One of the important tasks facing us is to take into account the advantages and disadvantages of energy production methods in secondary education and to minimize the impact of these disadvantages on the environment and the human factor. As technology develops in the energy sector, of course, side effects also arise.

Interest in alternative energy sources is growing. There is currently a need for specialists in this field.

Alternative energy is based on renewable energy sources. These include solar energy, wind energy, the internal heat of the planet, tidal energy, and ocean wave energy. All modern technological processes and production growth are possible thanks to reliable energy supply. One of the main tasks facing the world's leading engineers and scientists today is to obtain energy from renewable sources and preserve resources for the well-being of future generations.

Students at school will be able to learn more about this complex but promising work within the framework of the student's technology park project created by educational institutions. Such classes are aimed at studying the main areas of alternative energy and acquiring practical skills in these areas, and interest in this area develops in students from an early age. This can be an interesting and promising activity in which modern schoolchildren can realize themselves [16].

The principles of the Technopark project are as follows:

1. Study of the production and storage of energy resources;
2. Study of the processes of converting primary energy into secondary energy, the process of transferring secondary energy to the consumer;
3. Study of the principles of energy efficiency and energy saving in everyday life and production;
4. To become familiar in detail with the principles of operation of a power plant using renewable energy sources;
5. Study of the environmental aspects of traditional and alternative energy;

6. Free exploration of the possibilities of efficient use of natural resources.

Similar technology park projects are already being implemented in Chelyabinsk, Plashtyn, Magnitogorsk and other Russian cities so named “Kvantorium” [16].

Hydrogen is almost never found in free form on Earth; it needs to be produced. We know that in the era of “hydrogen production – hydrogen use,” losses are inevitable. Therefore, one of the important tasks of modern science is to find ways to produce hydrogen with minimal losses. Hydrogen is already used in many industries, even in the automotive industry. For example, China has announced the production of a hydrogen-powered car. To be ready for such innovations, it is important to create a children's technology park.

Within the framework of such a project, by creating new laboratories and equipping them with educational equipment, we create an opportunity for students to become familiar with the principles of operation of this production and to take direct part in this production. Thus, children see all types of energy and gain experience working with a generator.

Formation of the concept of "Green Energy"

First of all, it is necessary to provide students with information about nature, the role of man in nature, the role of nature in human life and the surrounding world. It is important to create an environment in which each student can share their thoughts and ideas by establishing a dialogue and an individual approach to each student. It is important to promote the ideas of nature conservation, to cultivate a sense of responsibility in the younger generation, to develop skills in saving energy and resources. Preparing independent work on topics directly and indirectly related to climate change, holding open lessons and evenings on this topic can also form a habit of caring for nature in children. This will also help develop skills in explaining natural processes.

The formation of the concept of "green energy" in schoolchildren can begin with an explanation of the basic principles and advantages, as well as practical examples and demonstrations of projects. It is necessary to teach children to distinguish renewable energy sources from traditional energy sources, to understand their positive impact on the environment and savings, to interest them in active participation in the implementation of environmentally friendly projects. The program for the formation of the concept of "green energy" can be divided into four parts:

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The Role of Artificial Intelligence in Renewable Energy Management

Artificial intelligence has the potential to revolutionize all areas of the industry, including education, which helps students reach their full potential and acquire the necessary skills. As AI technologies advance, it is becoming easier for educators to implement AI tools in their classrooms and provide personalized learning experiences. Using AI-based platforms, students can be taught how to manage renewable energy sources.

In recent years, many studies have been conducted to replace all traditional energy sources to reduce dependence on exhaustible fossil fuels and their harmful effects on the environment. Thus, green energy technology is considered as a future alternative to meet all energy needs and related services. The training of future personnel should start from school years by introducing them to this area and explaining it in their accessible language. In light of the future goals of using renewable energy, artificial intelligence (AI) is now the subject of ongoing research and development [18].

One of the major benefits of using artificial intelligence is the ability to manage energy using data. Modern energy management systems require fast and accurate data analysis to make decisions, and artificial intelligence helps automate this process. An important area where artificial intelligence can play a significant role is energy management in modern energy management systems. Artificial

intelligence can be used to analyze data and make predictions, which helps manage energy systems more efficiently.

Although the use of artificial intelligence has its own advantages, there are also risks associated with its use. Various risks are related to data security, data privacy, cybersecurity, etc. Renewable energy sources have certain limitations. For example, solar power generation systems, at the very first stage of conversion, are dependent on climatic conditions such as solar radiation, temperature, partial shading of the panel, etc. In addition, solar photovoltaic installations must, under any conditions, provide sufficient power to meet the associated load requirement. All these advantages and disadvantages need to be presented to students in an accessible language.

Thus, the use of artificial intelligence can improve the efficiency of energy production from solar photovoltaic systems and reduce the costs of its production and operation. Using artificial intelligence to optimize electricity production allows for increased resource efficiency and lower energy costs in the future. It also promotes the development of clean energy sources, which is an important step towards sustainable development [18].

Conclusion

To form the concept of "Green Energy" in secondary vocational education institutions, it is necessary to develop programs and implement projects that correspond to the age level of students. Within the framework of this project, students should acquire skills in constructing models and thinking in this area with the help of teachers. Since one of the promising tools for increasing the efficiency of renewable energy sources is artificial intelligence technology, subjects in this area should be included in the curriculum in order to prepare and attract interest in a promising area in the future. Conducting classes in a game form will allow students to learn to freely and confidently express their opinions, suggestions and ideas. Thus, a comprehensive personality for society and personnel in the field of energy and information technology are simultaneously formulated.

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